

TRANSMISSION OF MEASURING SIGNALS BY AN INVARIANT PROPERTY OF COMMUNICATION LINES WITH LOSSES

A. Penin and A. Sidorenko

*D. Ghitu Institute of Electronic Engineering and Nanotechnologies,
Academiei str.3/3, Chisinau, MD-2028 Republic of Moldova
E-mails: aapenin@mail.ru, anatoli.sidorenko@kit.edu*

(Received November 20, 2018)

Abstract

An invariant relationship between sets of load conductivity values and the respective values of the input currents of three wire communication lines is shown. This relationship does not depend on parameters of the lines and the accuracy of measuring devices. It allows transmitting signals of different physical sensors in the analog form for monitoring technical or natural objects.

Keywords: communication line, resistive sensor, projective transformation, cross ratio, projective coordinates

1. Introduction

Different sensors of physical values are used for monitoring technical or natural objects. For these—typically remote—devices, it is necessary to provide the transmission of measuring signals [1], for example, by multi-wire lines [2]. At present time, methods for transmitting discrete electrical signals in the binary code are used. These methods are known as the RS-485 and MicroLAN interfaces. Low noise immunity is a disadvantage of the known methods. Therefore, researches and elaborations of systems for transmitting discrete electrical signals in the analog form with an improved noise immunity are important [3–5]. However, two dedicated communication lines are necessary to transfer two signals. The point is that longitudinal and lateral resistive losses of actual lines do not allow using the common wire so as to apply more economical three-wire lines.

The theoretical researches show that an invariant relationship takes place between sets of load conductivity values and the respective values of the input currents of this line with losses [6–8]. The cross ratio of four points, known in projective geometry, is this invariant relationship [9]. Therefore, the value of cross ratio (ratio of two proportions) does not depend on parameters of the line and the accuracy of the measuring devices. These invariants are used for the transmission or, more precisely, restoration of measuring signals over three wire lines.

In the present paper, the obtained results are developed for the practical implementation of these transmission systems.

2. Foundation of the Transmission of Signals over a Line

We consider a four-port circuit in Fig. 1. Let us give necessary relationships between the input currents and load conductivities. So, we have

$$V_1 = I_1 / Y_{L1}, \quad V_2 = I_2 / Y_{L2}.$$

The family of straight lines $(I_1, I_2, Y_{L1}) = 0$, $(I_1, I_2, Y_{L2}) = 0$ at change of Y_{L1}, Y_{L2} is represented by two bunches of straight lines in the system of coordinates (I_1, I_2) in Fig. 2.

Fig. 1. Four port with variable load conductivities Y_{L1}, Y_{L2} .

Next, we use the idea of projective coordinates of a running regime point. Let the initial or running regime correspond to point M^1 , which is set by the values of conductivities Y_{L1}^1, Y_{L2}^1 and currents I_1^1, I_2^1 .

In addition, this point is defined by projective non-uniform coordinates m_1^1, m_2^1 and homogeneous coordinates $\xi_1^1, \xi_2^1, \xi_3^1$, which are set by the reference or coordinate triangle G_1, G_2 and a unit point SC .

The nonuniform projective coordinate, as the cross ratio of four points, has the form

$$m_1^1 = (Y_{L1}^{OC} \ Y_{L1}^1 \ Y_{L1}^{SC} \ Y_{L1}^{G1}) = \frac{Y_{L1}^1 - 0}{Y_{L1}^1 - Y_{L1}^{G1}} \div \frac{\infty - 0}{\infty - Y_{L1}^{G1}} = \frac{Y_{L1}^1}{Y_{L1}^1 - Y_{L1}^{G1}}, \quad m_2^1 = \frac{Y_{L2}^1}{Y_{L2}^1 - Y_{L2}^{G2}}. \quad (1)$$

Fig. 2. Two bunches of load straight lines with the parameters Y_{L1}, Y_{L2} .

In turn, the homogeneous projective coordinates ξ_1, ξ_2, ξ_3 set the nonuniform coordinates by

$$m_1 = \frac{\xi_1}{\xi_3}, \quad m_2 = \frac{\xi_2}{\xi_3}. \quad (2)$$

The homogeneous coordinates are defined as the ratio of distances $\delta_1^1, \delta_2^1, \delta_3^1$ of point M^1 and distances $\delta_1^{SC}, \delta_2^{SC}, \delta_3^{SC}$ of point SC to the sides of the coordinate triangle $G_1 0 G_2$:

$$\xi_1^1 = \frac{\delta_1^1}{\delta_1^{SC}} = \frac{I_1^1}{I_1^{SC}}, \quad \xi_2^1 = \frac{\delta_2^1}{\delta_2^{SC}} = \frac{I_2^1}{I_2^{SC}}, \quad \xi_3^1 = \frac{\delta_3^1}{\delta_3^{SC}} = \frac{I_3^1}{I_3^{SC}} \quad \rho \xi_3^1 = \frac{\delta_3^1}{\delta_3^{SC}}. \quad (3)$$

Let us consider the input currents (I_3, I_4) of our four-port. We may superpose the system of coordinates $(I_3 0 I_4)$ with the system of coordinates $(I_1 0 I_2)$ in Fig. 3. Then, any point M^1 with coordinates (I_1, I_2) corresponds to a point \bar{M}^1 with coordinates (I_3, I_4) .

In terms of geometry, a projective transformation that transfers points of the (I_1, I_2) plane into points of the (I_3, I_4) plane takes place. Therefore, the reference triangle $G_1 0 G_2$, the SC point, and the running regime point M^1 correspond to triangle $\bar{G}_1 \bar{0} \bar{G}_2$, point \bar{SC} , and point \bar{M}^1 , as shown by arrows.

Next, the axes of currents I_1, I_2 correspond to axes \bar{I}_1, \bar{I}_2 . In addition, two bunches of the straight lines $(I_1, I_2, Y_{L1})=0$, $(I_1, I_2, Y_{L2})=0$ correspond to two bunches of the lines $(I_3, I_4, Y_{L1})=0$, $(I_3, I_4, Y_{L2})=0$ with centers at points \bar{G}_2, \bar{G}_1 . Thus, point \bar{M}^1 is set by other currents I_3^1, I_4^1 . In addition, this point is defined by projective nonuniform and homogeneous coordinates, which are set by the reference triangle $\bar{G}_1 \bar{0} \bar{G}_2$ and a unit point \bar{SC} .

Fig. 3. Projective transformation of the (I_1, I_2) plane onto the (I_3, I_4) plane.

The property of projective transformations shows that the point \bar{M}^1 coordinates are equal to the point M^1 coordinates, as these points M^1, \bar{M}^1 are set by the same loads Y_{L1}^1, Y_{L2}^1 . Therefore, this property gives required invariant relations between the input and output currents. To find the point \bar{M}^1 projective coordinates, it is necessary to use the equations of sides of the reference triangle. Finally, we obtain the nonuniform coordinates by the input currents:

$$m_1 = \frac{C_{11}I_3 + C_{12}I_4 + 1}{C_{31}I_3 + C_{32}I_4 - 1}, \quad m_2 = \frac{C_{21}I_3 + C_{22}I_4 + 1}{C_{31}I_3 + C_{32}I_4 - 1}. \quad (4)$$

Using running values of input currents, we find or, more precisely, restore the values of nonuniform coordinates (9). Then, the values of given load conductivities are calculated according to the inverse expressions $Y_{L1}(m_1), Y_{L2}(m_2)$ to (1).

This formulated algorithm is of practical interest for the transfer of two sensing signals via a three-wire line; it makes it possible to separate (or restore) two signals by the input currents (five pairs of the currents) of the line.

In actual practice, the characteristic values of the input and output currents (as the vertexes of the coordinate triangles and unit points) are precalculated by testing the line. To do so, in a short time slot, the five pairs of load conductivity sets (test and information values) are transmitted. There are test conductivities $Y_{L1}^{OC}, Y_{L1}^{SC}, Y_{L1}^{G1}, Y_{L2}^{OC}, Y_{L2}^{SC}, Y_{L2}^{G2}$ and information conductivities Y_{L1}^1, Y_{L2}^1 . Usually, the test scale conductivities $Y_{L1}^{G1} < 0, Y_{L2}^{G2} < 0$. Therefore, the respective output currents submit to terms $I_1^{G1} > I_1^{SC}, I_2^{G2} > I_2^{SC}$. These large test values complicate the practical implementation. Therefore, we will consider the easily testable transmission system [10] in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. System of transmission of two sensor signals.

3. Easily Testable Transmission System

At first, in a short time slot, five pairs of test load conductivity sets are transmitted. There are test conductivities $Y_{L1}^{OC}, Y_{L1}^{SC}, Y_{L1}^{REF}, Y_{L2}^{OC}, Y_{L2}^{SC}, Y_{L2}^{REF}$, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Correspondence between the test load conductivities and the output and input currents

Set	Load conductivities		Output currents		Input currents	
1	$Y_{L1}^{OC} = 0$	$Y_{L2}^{OC} = 0$	$I_1^{OC} = 0$	$I_2^{OC} = 0$	I_3^{OC}	I_4^{OC}
2	$Y_{L1}^{OC} = 0$	$Y_{L2}^{SC} = \infty$	$I_1^{OC,SC} = 0$	$I_2^{OC,SC}$	$I_3^{OC,SC}$	$I_4^{OC,SC}$
3	$Y_{L1}^{SC} = \infty$	$Y_{L2}^{OC} = 0$	$I_1^{SC,OC}$	$I_2^{SC,OC} = 0$	$I_3^{SC,OC}$	$I_4^{SC,OC}$
4	$Y_{L1}^{SC} = \infty$	$Y_{L2}^{SC} = \infty$	I_1^{SC}	I_2^{SC}	I_3^{SC}	I_4^{SC}
5	Y_{L1}^{REF}	Y_{L2}^{REF}	I_1^{REF}	I_2^{REF}	-	-

For clarity, we give the geometrical interpretation of the obtained sets similarly to Fig. 2. The family of straight lines $(I_1, I_2, Y_{L1})=0$, $(I_1, I_2, Y_{L2})=0$ for the test load conductivities is represented by the two bunches of straight lines in the system of coordinates (I_1, I_2) in Fig. 5.

Let us consider the following points. Points $I_1^{SC,OC}$, $I_2^{OC,SC}$ are situated accordingly on axes I_1 and I_2 . Coordinates I_1^{SC}, I_2^{SC} and I_1^{REF}, I_2^{REF} determinate points SC, REF .

Fig. 5. Two bunches of load straight lines with the test parameters.

As noted above, currents I_1^{G1}, I_2^{G2} considerably exceed currents I_1^{SC}, I_2^{SC} . Then, we can determine scale conductivity Y_{L1}^{G1} corresponding to coordinate $(I_1^{G1}, 0)$ (as the intersection of the straight line passing through points $I_2^{OC,SC}, SC$ with axis I_1).

The straight line $(I_2^{OC,SC}, SC)$ equation is as follows:

$$\frac{I_2}{I_2^{OC,SC}} + \frac{(I_2^{OC,SC} - I_2^{SC}) \cdot I_1}{I_2^{OC,SC} I_1^{SC}} - 1 = 0.$$

For current $I_2 = 0$, point G_1 corresponds to the current

$$I_1^{G1} = \frac{I_2^{OC,SC} \cdot I_1^{SC}}{I_2^{OC,SC} - I_2^{SC}}. \quad (5)$$

Similarly, scale conductivity Y_{L2}^{G2} corresponds to coordinate $(I_1^{G1}, 0)$ or point G_2 . Then

$$I_2^{G2} = \frac{I_1^{SC,OC} \cdot I_2^{SC}}{I_1^{SC,OC} - I_1^{SC}}. \quad (6)$$

Let us introduce the homogeneous coordinate $\xi_1^{REF}, \xi_2^{REF}, \xi_3^{REF}$ of point REF :

$$\xi_1^{REF} = \frac{\delta_1^{REF}}{\delta_1^{SC}} = \frac{I_1^{REF}}{I_1^{SC}}, \quad \xi_2^{REF} = \frac{\delta_2^{REF}}{\delta_2^{SC}} = \frac{I_2^{REF}}{I_2^{SC}}, \quad \xi_3^{REF} = \frac{\delta_3^{REF}}{\delta_3^{SC}}. \quad (7)$$

We use the distances to the sides of triangle $G_1 O G_2$. In particular, for the equation of the straight line $G_1 G_2$

$$\frac{I_2}{I_2^{G2}} + \frac{I_1}{I_1^{G1}} - 1 = 0,$$

and the coordinate

$$\xi_3^{REF} = \frac{\delta_3^{REF}}{\delta_3^{SC}} = \frac{\frac{I_2^{REF}}{I_2^{G2}} + \frac{I_1^{REF}}{I_1^{G1}} - 1}{\frac{I_2^{SC}}{I_2^{G2}} + \frac{I_1^{SC}}{I_1^{G1}} - 1} \quad (8)$$

and further the nonuniform projective coordinates

$$m_1^{REF} = \frac{\xi_1^{REF}}{\xi_3^{REF}}, m_2^{REF} = \frac{\xi_2^{REF}}{\xi_3^{REF}}. \quad (9)$$

On the other hand,

$$m_1^{REF} = (Y_{L1}^{OC} Y_{L1}^{REF} Y_{L1}^{SC} Y_{L1}^{G1}) = \frac{Y_{L1}^{REF}}{Y_{L1}^{REF} - Y_{L1}^{G1}}, \quad m_2^{REF} = \frac{Y_{L2}^{REF}}{Y_{L2}^{REF} - Y_{L2}^{G2}}.$$

Finally, for the load current values and the known test conductivities, the scale conductivity calculator gives the required values

$$Y_{L1}^{G1} = Y_{L1}^{REF} \frac{m_1^{REF} - 1}{m_1^{REF}}, \quad Y_{L2}^{G2} = Y_{L2}^{REF} \frac{m_2^{REF} - 1}{m_2^{REF}}. \quad (10)$$

Next, let us use the geometrical interpretation of input currents I_3, I_4 in Fig. 4. We determine the coordinates (I_3^{G1}, I_4^{G1}) of point \bar{G}_1 (as the intersection of the straight line passing through points $I_4^{OC,SC}, \bar{SC}$ with axis \bar{I}_1).

The straight line $(I_4^{OC,SC}, \bar{SC})$ equation is as follows:

$$(I_3^{SC} - I_3^{OC,SC})I_4 + (I_4^{OC,SC} - I_4^{SC})I_3 + (I_4^{SC}I_3^{OC,SC} - I_3^{SC}I_4^{OC,SC}) = 0. \quad (11)$$

The straight line $\bar{0}, I_3^{SC,OC}$ or the axis \bar{I}_1 equation has the form

$$A_{01}I_4 + B_{01}I_3 + C_{01} = 0,$$

where

$$A_{01} = I_3^{SC,OC} - I_3^{OC}, \quad B_{01} = I_4^{OC} - I_4^{SC,OC}, \quad C_{01} = I_4^{SC,OC}I_3^{OC} - I_4^{OC}I_3^{SC,OC}. \quad (12)$$

Owing to these equations, we obtain coordinates (I_3^{G1}, I_4^{G1}) . Similarly, we determine coordinates (I_3^{G2}, I_4^{G2}) of point \bar{G}_2 .

The straight line $I_3^{SC,OC}, \bar{SC}$ equation is as follows:

$$(I_3^{SC} - I_3^{SC,OC})I_4 + (I_4^{SC,OC} - I_4^{SC})I_3 + (I_4^{SC}I_3^{SC,OC} - I_3^{SC}I_4^{SC,OC}) = 0. \quad (13)$$

Fig. 4. Input characteristics of the line as coordinate system $\bar{G}_1 \bar{0} \bar{G}_2$.

The straight line $\bar{O}, I_4^{OC,SC}$ or axis \bar{I}_2 equation is as follows:

$$A_{02}I_4 + B_{02}I_3 + C_{02} = 0,$$

where

$$A_{02} = I_3^{OC,SC} - I_3^{OC}, B_{02} = I_4^{OC} - I_4^{OC,SC}, C_{02} = I_4^{OC,SC}I_3^{OC} - I_4^{OC}I_3^{OC,SC}. \quad (14)$$

Owing to these equations, we obtain coordinates (I_3^{G2}, I_4^{G2}) .

In addition, we give the equation of the straight line passing through points \bar{G}_2, \bar{G}_1

$$A_{12}I_4 + B_{12}I_3 + C_{12} = 0,$$

where

$$A_{12} = I_3^{G2} - I_3^{G1}, B_{12} = I_4^{G2} - I_4^{G1}, C_{12} = I_4^{G2}I_3^{G1} - I_4^{G1}I_3^{G2}. \quad (15)$$

The stage of preliminary testing and calculations is finished at this point.

Next, cross ratios (1) are accepted also as transmitted signals Y_{S1}, Y_{S2} . Then, using (5)–(10), the information conductivities are precomputed by units F :

$$Y_{L1} = \frac{Y_{L1}^{G1} \cdot Y_{S1}}{Y_{S1} - 1}, Y_{L2} = \frac{Y_{L2}^{G2} \cdot Y_{S2}}{Y_{S2} - 1}.$$

Using the input currents, we calculate homogeneous projective coordinates ξ_1, ξ_2, ξ_3 . In the given case, the homogeneous coordinates are defined as the ratio of distances $\bar{\delta}_1, \bar{\delta}_2, \bar{\delta}_3$ of point \bar{M} and distances $\bar{\delta}_1^{SC}, \bar{\delta}_2^{SC}, \bar{\delta}_3^{SC}$ of point \bar{SC} to the sides of the coordinate triangle $\bar{G}_1 \bar{O} \bar{G}_2$ by (11)–(15):

$$\xi_1 = \frac{\bar{\delta}_1}{\bar{\delta}_1^{SC}} = \frac{A_{02}I_4 + B_{02}I_3 + C_{02}}{A_{02}I_4^{SC} + B_{02}I_3^{SC} + C_{02}}, \quad \xi_2 = \frac{\bar{\delta}_2}{\bar{\delta}_2^{SC}} = \frac{A_{01}I_4 + B_{01}I_3 + C_{01}}{A_{01}I_4^{SC} + B_{01}I_3^{SC} + C_{01}}, \quad (16)$$

$$\xi_3 = \frac{\bar{\delta}_3}{\bar{\delta}_3^{SC}} = \frac{A_{12}I_4 + B_{12}I_3 + C_{12}}{A_{12}I_4^{SC} + B_{12}I_3^{SC} + C_{12}}.$$

Therefore, transmitted signals Y_{S1}, Y_{S2} by (16) are as follows:

$$m_1 = Y_{S1} = \frac{\xi_1}{\xi_3}, m_2 = Y_{S2} = \frac{\xi_2}{\xi_3}.$$

4. Conclusions

An invariant relationship between regime parameters at the input and output of a communication line takes place. The proposed selection of line parameters makes it possible to introduce projective coordinates for the easily testable transmission system. Input projective coordinates allow finding load conductivities only by the measured input currents without running determination of the transmission parameters of this line. It allows transmitting signals

over a communication line. The obtained results can be a basis for carrying out applied researches and developments; in particular, results can be extended to AC lines.

Acknowledgments. The authors are grateful to acad. V. Postolati and Prof. D. Maevski for useful discussion of results and to STCU#6329 and “SPINTECH–TWINNING” projects for financial support.

References

- [1] K. Walker, M. Ramplin, US Patent 6 459 363 B1 (2002).
- [2] A. Aldereguia, G. Richter, and J. Williams, US Patent 7 502 991 B2 (2009).
- [3] V. Ovchinnikov, US Patent 8 446 977 B2 (2013).
- [4] V. Ovchinnikov, RF Patent 2 250 566 (2005).
- [5] V. Ovchinnikov, RF Patent 2 435 303 (2011).
- [6] A. Penin, *Analysis of Electrical Circuits with Variable Load Regime Parameters: Projective Geometry Method*. 2nd Ed, Springer International Publishing AG Switzerland, 417 p., 2016.
- [7] A. Penin and A. Sidorenko, Transmission of measuring signals and power supply of remote sensors, in: J. Bonca, S. Kruchinin, eds., *Nanotechnology in the Security Systems*, NATO Science for Peace and Security Series C: Environmental Security: Springer, 267 p., 2014.
- [8] A. Penin and A. Sidorenko, Transmission of three resistance sensor signals over four wire lines with losses, in: J. Bonca, S. Kruchinin, eds., *Nanomaterials for Security*. NATO Science for Peace and Security Series A: Chemistry and Biology: Springer, 311 p., 2016.
- [9] J. A. Frank, *Schaum's Outline of Theory and Problems of Projective Geometry*, Schaum Publishing Company, 243 p., 1967.
- [10] A. Penin, A. Sidorenko, and S. Donu, MD Patent 1242 (2018).